

Sociopolitical Oppression and Suppression in Soyinka's *A Play of Giant*

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Abstract

The concept of oppression is one of the most vital concepts in contemporary political discourses in the literary works. This concept has some interdisciplinary characteristics which are associated with culture, religion, sociology and politics. Therefore, this paper critically explores various sociopolitical oppression and suppression of Africans by their leaders (fellow Africans) in most parts of the continent as portrayed by Wole Soyinka. The paper reveals how African leaders misuse power, serve their personal interest instead of the citizens who voted them to power. In the *Play of Giant*, Soyinka uses satire to depict the attitude of many African leaders towards their citizens. It shows that the leaders have less sympathy towards the masses. It also shows inferiority complex, dictatorship, abuse of power, intolerance, immorality, and insensitiveness of African leaders which are all against the African cultures but inherited from colonialism.

Keywords: *Sociopolitical, Oppression, Suppression, A play of Giant.*

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Introduction

Oppression results in a “discontinuity” between these groups and brings about contradictory relations in the traditional Nigerian society. Likewise, imperial schemes go along with “expansionism, and as a loosely microcosmic space in which the dynamics of colonisation is prefigured in a parodic and casual form” (Chrisman, 2003, p.28). The Nigerian society underwent this oppressive phase during the early periods of imperial colonialism.

Oppression is an ethical phenomenon in the human history. In African literary works, it was created through various stages as per the countries' requirement for slaves and homegrown issues. The slave masters attempted to carry slaves from a few world districts to fulfill their requirements and to fabricate an efficient society which they tried to accomplish. In this situation, the experts and their slaves gain relations on the grounds of racial issues. They appreciate and pass judgment on one another based on power and control. The slaves, from one perspective, feel that they are enslaved and

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taken advantage of by their strong colonizers. Then again, the experts feel that they have outright command over their slaves. In the middle of this connection, another pilgrim sense springs out. The concept of a master and a slave was introduced. The masters are the controlling power, whereas the slaves are the controlled minority (Thiam, 1995).

The political as well as the historical personal attributes of Nigerian colonialism are formidable. The fictional writings, consequently, serve as biographical documentation of some periods of this colonialism. However, oppression indirectly universalizes these experiences through the Nigeria colonial periods. This universal documentation encompasses the Nigerian society as a victim of wars. The harsh economic conditions had left their apparent impact upon the essential Nigerian culture. Oppression conveys the life of those which become victims at the hands of colonialism. In this case, this experience becomes universal i.e., the lives of the Nigerian natives are a stereotype of all British oppression that inflicted the harsh military domination over the Nigerian lands (Imoh-Itah, Amadi and Akpan, 2016).

The imperial colonialism causes detrimental colonial settlement. This settlement does not change the colonizer. It mainly changes the Nigerian colonized territory. The imperial colonialism suits within a certain discourse which “has really been lost is a sense of the density and interdependence of human life, which can neither be reduced to a formula nor be brushed aside as irrelevant” (Said, 1979, p.30). Said’s (1979) explication of colonial discourse corresponds to the corruption realities during colonialism. Such kind of colonial discourse has a conspicuous circulation of the contradiction between two different cultures, and therefore, it yields a special and an accepted agreement where “the mere repression of colonial memories is never, in itself, tantamount to a surpassing of or emancipation from the uncomfortable realities of the colonial encounter” (Gandhi, 1998, p.4).

The concepts of oppression and protest are played out in the definition of Nigerian culture. The critical nuances of cultural identity in post-colonial theory relate to individuals seeking refuge from the “other’s” advent. Thus, identity involves a “desire” to preserve the national identity. Consequently, the individuals’ identity maybe refers to “the relatively stronger desire to define their cultural identity” (Talib, 2002, p.21). These tragic events represent the powerful national resistance to the Whites. Such resistance implies a national desire to maintain the aboriginal culture that will be approached in Soyinka’s *A Play of Giants*.

Oppression in Wole Soyinka attempt to capture the conflicts that took place between the old African traditions in the Nigerian society and the new western culture (Kushwaha&Naseem, 2000). The socio-political and religious undertones in Wole Soyinka’s plays are evident in various myth, rituals and sacrifices. The abuse of power, brutality and violation of human rights are portrayed in his selected plays (Ogundokun, 2014). Therefore, the present study attempts to specifically focus on oppression and protest in Soyinka’s *A Play of Giants*. The study will conduct a postcolonial analysis of oppression. Oppression is the result of colonialism per se, or the colonizers inflict bitter treatment upon the colonized people. Therefore, oppression is the cruel result of this treatment. As a deduction, post-colonialism is the fitting approach to conduct the study of oppression and protest through analyzing oppression, clash of culture and resistance.

Literature Review

The play happens at the Bulgarian Government office in Assembled Countries, New York. It began with three of the authoritative African leaders, Kamini who is the host, and Kasco and Gunma who want to find a hobby-size bunch model of the 'delegated heads' in their similarity. They aim to make their sculptures part of different sculptures that would be put at the UN step section. Their conversation on power and administration was interfered with by the presence of the Director of the Bugara National Bank who brought insight into the refusal of the World Bank to concede Bugara country the requested credit because of the ground of unsatisfied circumstances to which the Bugaran President, Life President, Kamini, answered that the Executive ought to return and consent to at all conditions set forward by the World Bank even to the detriment of the Bugaran public's body and soul.

The setting is East and Central Africa such as Uganda, Zaire, Central African Republic and Equatorial Guinea. It presents and recreates the experiences of the people of these countries in the nineteen seventies (1970s).

It has the accompanying characters: Benefacio Gunema, Emperor Kasco, Field-Marshal Kamini who will be the focal character, General Bara Tuboum (These are the four African Head of State), Gudrum, a Scandinavian journalist, Executive of the Bugara National Bank, Stone worker, Bugaran Envoy, City chairman of Hyacombe, Teacher Batey, Two Russian Representatives, Two American Representatives, Team specials, Watchmen and Secretary-General of the Unified Countries.

As a preface or break, the writer acquaints the characters with the peruser toward the start and throughout the play separately. He takes a gander at the similarity between the African Heads of State and ongoing verifiable characters that have been excessively articulated; pioneers like Macias Nguema (late) of Tropical Guinea, Jean Baptiste Bokassa of the Focal African Republic, Mobutu Sese Koko of Congo Kinshasa and the Legend of legends, the Field Marshal El-Haji Dr. Idi Amin of Uganda.

Generally, the play is a satirical one, it mainly discusses socio-political oppression, inferiority complex, dictatorship, abuse of power, intolerance, immorality, and insensitiveness of African leaders which are all against the African cultures but inherited from colonialism. Therefore, the paper explores how socio-political oppression and suppression are portrayed by Soyinka in the Play of Giant.

Result

The play was coded and categorized in themes to answer the research questions. The following sections present the themes which are supported by excerpts from the play.

A Quest to Impress Imperialist Countries

Soyinka reveals oppression and suppression of Africans by African leaders who are against African culture, well-being and have low self-esteem. They are Western Sycophants and supporters particularly Gudrum, professor Batey as well, chairman Central Bank. Imperialist have no regards for African and African cultures, they introduced inferiority complex. Thus, many Africans learnt from them. Anything made in Africa or made for Africans is regarded as bad. In Nigeria for instance, made-in-Nigeria products are considered of low or poor quality. People prefer to buy made in china than that of Nigeria. Through his characters and characterization Soyinka exposes and follies this attitude of African. For instance, when chairman of the

Bugaran central bank compared the Bugaran currency with tissue papers right in front of the president, Kamini. This made Kamini protested in order to get their self-respect. He went ahead to tortures and kill him. Though the punishment seems severe, it would serve as deterrent to others.

KAMINI. What? What you say just now?

CHAIRMAN. Your Excellency?

KAMINI. I say, what you talking just now about Bugara currency? ·

CHAIRMAN. Just that all currency needs backing Your Excellency. It must be . . .

KAMINI. No, you said Bugara currency only worth something this and that.

CHAIRMAN. Oh. I was trying to explain that any paper money is only worth what . . . (He trails off)

KAMINI (rising). You saying Bugara currency only worth shit paper? Is that what I hear you say just now? Is that what I hear you say just now?

CHAIRMAN. Your Excellency, I was only trying to illustrate . . .

KAMINI (to KASCO and GUNEMA). You see, is this kind of traitor I have in charge of Bugara Central Bank. This syphilitic bastard talking worse than imperialist propaganda.

CHAIRMAN. Your Excellency . . .

KAMINI. Is no wonder Bugara getting broke all the time, when this kind of chairman insulting Bugara national currency, calling it shit paper to everybody. This the kind of person going to important meeting of World Bank to ask for loan. You think World Bank give Bugara loan when you calling national currency shit paper?

CHAIRMAN (falling on his knees). My Life President, I assure Your Excellency I never . . .

KAMINI. Today I make you eat good old Bugara shit. (He reaches for the bell.)

CHAIRMAN (abject with terror). Your Excellency, my Life President ... (p 7)

Soyinka also used his character, Kasco in this play to indict African leaders of their poor or low self-esteem. He is a neo-colonial stooge who represents the image of the francophone leaders who are French black men. To him, everything French is good and better, we should accept them. Despite the fact that his country is an independent state, he still allows French government to control the country. Kasco stands for many African leaders who sold back the country including the peasants to the colonial masters. He is an example of African leaders who after champion the cause of struggle for independence turn round to accept the wolf of yesterday to be sheep of today. Through the character of Kasco, Soyinka exposes and ridicules the African leaders who are midwives of the imperialists.

Corrupt Practices of African Leaders

Corruption is one of the keys through which African leaders oppress their citizens. Soyinka in this play, as portrayed through the characters of the leader, Kamini, Kasco Gunema and Tuboum points out to us that the leader instead of serving their people, tend to serve their selfish interest. They sacrifice the welfare of their citizens for their enjoyment. In African societies, corruption is one of the deadly diseases believed to be the legacy of colonialism. Many Africans learnt to exploit, fellow Africans from the colonial masters in which corruption is one of the means. Corruption is not part of the African culture but inherited from the colonial masters. Africans are known to be helpers of one another. However, with the coming of the colonial masters, many African learnt to exploit their fellows or their states. In Nigeria today, corruption is known to be practiced by many. In the *A Play of Giant*, Soyinka portrayed how corruption was originally learnt from the colonial masters and how it was rejected by Africans initially. For instance, a state minister played a trick in order to run away with the state's fund but was detected by Kamini.

KAMINI. What fools! Did they not notice that they can no longer hear anything? Did they think the delegation was sleeping or what?

AMBASSADOR. Your Gracious Excellency, they were clever. They left on a tape recorder of conversations which must have kept running for an hour or more.

KAMINI. You see. Is it not a disgrace? A whole minister of state, he is playing tricks like 007 James Bond in order to run away with national funds. That is the kind of ministers left in Bugara. James Bond. That is what result from imperialism and neo-colonialism and the culture they teach our people. Syphilitic culture. Mental syphilis. How you (p15)

Surprisingly, Kamini himself was not free from corruption and other exploitation of his fellow Africans. He could afford renting expensive hotels and give gifts to white folks any how while many Bugarian peasants are starving. In recent years, many African leaders are like that. They make unnecessary trips to American and European

countries. They lavish their country's resources. There by creating a lot of debt for their people. Here Soyinka is portraying the foolishness of some African leaders who forget that they have people whom they are in power to serve by not noting this point the leaders have betrayal the people and Soyinka in this play is exposing the wickedness of the leaders through the theme of betrayal.

After from corruption, many African leaders are insensitive to the plight and living condition of their fellow Africans. They do not care for their countries or their masses but for themselves. This is also not part of the original African culture but as the result of colonialism. Soyinka uses his character, Kamini in this play to depict typical nature of many African leaders. Kamini takes political and economic decisions without any knowledge of economics and international politics or understanding the consequences of his action. For instance, he requests for loan from the World Bank at all cost without considering the needs of his people. "What I care about condition. Agree to any condition. Just get the loan" (p.5). A sensitive and responsible leader will not behave like Kamini. However, many African leaders are like that. When it comes to loan or any agreement to do with the Whites, they are like "show me where to sign and I will sign" without considering anything. Thus, Soyinka exposes as the result of colonialism, as clash of African culture, and ridicules and scorn such leaders.

Nigerian reality is also represented in the play through the epidemic of corruption and bribery. One of the leading figures in postcolonial theory and studies, Edward Said, believes that the consequences of colonialism are still persisting in the form of corruption and bribery, which permeates the development of many ex-colonies (Hammadi, 2014). The African ruling class inherited the moral decay of corruption and perpetuated it after independence. This is evident in most African countries including Nigeria, as Gumede (2012) opines that, "most of the African ruling parties and leaders lack the political will to genuinely tackle corruption".

In *A Play of Giant*, Soyinka captures these realities of corruption and bribery of Nigeria and Africa at large through the exhibition of the flamboyant life of the African head of states. The supreme leader of the Federal Republic of Bugara laments that whenever he is out of the country, his people, "wearing European coat and tie and forging signature of this and that bank manager", steal money from the government treasury or "bribe the guards and smuggle out" perceived traitors of his government. In fact, he concludes that "there is so much corruption" in the country. However, it is obvious that Dr. Life President Kamini does not have the political will to fight corruption because he is fully aware that "there are no funds" to settle civil servants' salaries, yet he moves on to spend millions of Naira for his sculpture to be displayed at the United Nation. In the Play of Giants, even the leaders proudly discuss on how they engage in corrupt practices; how the maltreat their people in the name of controlling them. For instance, Gunema claims that he supervises and surveillances his subjects from wherever he is on earth.

KAMINI. I do that too. But sometimes they bribe the guards
and smuggle out the families. There is so much corruption.

One man cannot supervise everting.

KASCO. Never?

GUNEMA. Never. It never happens. Even my political prisoners

I see when they begin to plan escape from prison.
TUBOUM. Lucky for you. You've only got a small island,
easily patrolled by a canoe or two with outboard motor.
Do you know the sheer size of Mbangi·Gwela? Even I don't
know half of what is inside it. (p. 26)

The political reality of Africa and Nigeria, in particular, is also portrayed by Soyinka. In many African societies, leaders impose themselves on their citizen. Soyinka in this play, *A Play of Giants* exposes the crude system whereby men are being forced to him ruled by leaders who they no longer have confidence in the people demonstrate their lack of confident in Barra Toboum by rebelling against him. Barra Tuboum is an epitome of leadership our society who imposes themselves on their people. Many African leaders are in power not because they want to serve people but they impose themselves on the people to serve their selfish interest. In Nigeria for instance, many of the elections conducted are characterized with various sort of malpractices such as rigging, ballot snatching, vote buying from the electorates. As the result, right people are voted into power. For instance, in the excerpt below Soyinka shows how professor Bartey explains to the president clearly the problem of their country but the president did not listen.

MAYOR. Professor . . . Professor Batey . . .

BATEY. What?

MAYOR. We have an immediate problem.

BATEY. I beg your pardon.

MAYOR. That's all right. It's all in your address, so save it.

Your Excellences, I have thought up a solution - if you will
be so kind a to indulge us. We must f a new appointment.

Give us time to get more keys. And Professor Batey of course
will have to include all Your Excellences in his address.

GUDRUM. With your permission, Your Excellency, just what I
was going to suggest. We must use the occasion to make
history. The embassy will fix a new time which gives us time
to invite the Press and television. (p.23)

Discussion

Inferiority of Africans

Through the manifestations of socio-cultural doubleness of a society, Homi Bhabha, in his classic essay, *The Location of Culture* (1994) calls this doubleness 'hybridity' and simply defines it as a "... dissembling image of being in, at least, two places at once". It is a meeting point of the entire two different cultures in societies. Because of its

colonial experience of more than five decades, Nigeria suffers from the syndrome of hybridity. In other words, the people are neither fully Africans nor Europeans; they are at crossroads with no idea on which path to follow. Nigerians, largely depend on the 'logic of mimicry' of the colonizers' culture in many ways- from language to clothing, food, customs, leadership and gestures. In these plays, Soyinka aptly captures this socio-cultural reality, exposing its impurity as a mere 'resemblance and menace' (Bhabha: *Of Mimicry and Man: The Ambivalence of Colonial Discourse*. 1996:362).

In *A Play of Giants*, for instance, the scenes and events largely take place at Bugaran Embassy of the United Nation Building, New York. Though the setting, according to an analyst, depicts the social, political and economic happenings in Uganda, Zaire, Central African Republic and Equatorial Guinea, it could also be argued that it reflects Nigerian people, projecting the hybridized reality of post-colonial Nigeria. One of these realities is notably evident in the representation of clothing of the African leaders at the UN building. In the stage direction of part one, Soyinka describes the outfit of Kamini, Kasco and Gunema in a typical western style. He writes:

One of the figures, a huge man (KAMINI) is in military dress uniform, its massive frontage covered in medals. On one side of him is a comparatively dwarfish creature (KASCO) who appears to be a deliberate parody of the big man. His costume is the same, down to the last medal. In addition, however, he wears a cloak of imperial purple. Flanking the central figure on the other side is a tall, thin man (GUNEMA) in tails of immaculate cut. His own decorations consist simply of a red sash and blue rosette, plus a medal or two. (p1)

These are supposed African leaders in the faraway USA, representing Africa and its people at UN General Assembly. It would have been a pride for them to wear African traditional attires as good ambassadors of the continent, instead, they put the western dress, promoting the western cultural values while neglecting African norms of clothing. This is also the reality of Nigerian postcolonial dictators. Most of the military dictators are like that; they dressed in the attires that did not in any way represent Nigerian culture. In fact, they prefer to be *White*, their colonizers than to be Africans as could be seen in the following excerpt from *A Play of Giants*.

GUNEMA. Size is not important. I know everything.

KASCO. Well, I have no problems of escapees. We are French.

My government: people are proud to be French, all my officials. To try to escape from Ia France - mon Dieu

who ever heard of such a thing?

KAINI. My brothers, let us go and eat. It is long pa time for food. We continue our discussion of politics over a good dinner, not so?

KASCO. Ah oui. Moi, j'ai faim. (p.26)

Another phenomenon that notably reflects the hybridized reality of Nigerian society in the play is language use of the colonized populations. Thomas B. Klein—in his very useful study, *Linguistic Identity, Agency, and Consciousness in Creole*—avers that as a

consequence of colonialism, native languages in so many colonized communities are relegated for domestic purposes or, at most, replaced by the language of the colonizer, though in some cases, the postcolonial populations use their own mother tongue “to respond to the imposition of a colonial tongue”. However, in these plays, the native languages are “diminished or lost”, they are hardly heard. The characters always communicate in a foreign language(s), without regards to their native tongues.

The long conversation between Kamini, Kasco, Taboun and Gunema at the UN building is completely carried out in the English language, which is more threatening to the indigenous African languages. Even the familiar “code-switching efforts that took place in such politicized and polarized environments” (Klein, 32) in which mother tongue(s) cut in spontaneously, the French Portuguese languages were used instead. For instance, “we -exist, I think, in a rare space which is - power. *Es 'Uerdad, no?'*(2), “Oui, oui. Le pouvoir, c'est a nous” (10), “*Mes condolences, camarade.*, “But these are the tiny...thorns that trouble the head of crown...*Si. Que lastima*” (16).

Conclusion

The paper explores the socio-political oppression and suppression in Soyinka’s *A play of giant*. The study reveals various ways in which African leaders oppress and suppress their citizens such as through corrupt practices of African leaders and their quest to impress imperialist countries. The study further reveals that many African leaders use inferiority complex to oppress and suppress their followers.

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